

A Study on Customer Satisfaction towards Online Shopping in Flipkart in Coimbatore city

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ABSTRACT

Flipkart are one of the leading online shopping websites in India. In this paper an attempt has been made to find customers satisfaction towards and flipkart. A sample of 50 respondent's were conveniently selected from Coimbatore District. The findings were analyzed using simple percentage analysis, ranking test. Findings reveal that female customers whose annual income is high are highly satisfied towards and flipkart. The research also concludes that even though is giving branded and quality product but customer are very much attracted towards the best services of flipkart.

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INTRODUCTION:

Customer satisfaction is a term frequently used in marketing. It is a measure of how products and services supplied meet or surpass customer expectation. Customer satisfaction is defined as "the number of customers or percentage of total customers, whose reported experience with a firm, its product, or its service exceeds specified satisfaction goals". In a survey made by senior marketing managers, they found that the customer satisfaction matrices is very useful tool in managing and monitoring their business. In a competitive marketplace where business compete for customers, customer satisfaction is seen as a key differentiation and increasingly has become a key elements of business strategy. It is essential for businesses to effectively manage customer satisfaction. To be able do this, firms need reliable and representative measures of satisfaction study is made on customer satisfaction on online products of flipkart in the district of Coimbatore.

REVIEWS OF LITERATURE

Rotem-mindali, O, salomon, and I.(2006) have studied the study was to develop a conceptual model of the decisions households make with regard to information gathering, purchase transactions and delivery mode. To collect data, they have developed a structured questionnaire and respondents were asked to assess a large variety of aspects concerning their shopping habits, preferences as well as attributes concerning their accessibility to and usage of IT-based applications. They found that a number of

respondents use internet to collect the information before newer and younger generation of organized retail industry evolution which is multidimensional and far more advanced than its previous generation.

Plessis, P., mostert, P., north, E. (2004) studied the relationship between the period of internal usage and online buying pattern of consumer. They have used data collection method and responses were received. They found that the period of internal usage significantly influenced the decision to purchase via the internet. Another finding was that period of internal usage significantly influenced whether those shopping on the internet searched for, or considered searching for, product and service information online prior to purchasing from non-internet-based sellers.

Kim, D., yang, Z., jun, M. (2003) made a study to identify key underlying dimensions of online retailing service quality as perceived by online customers. For the study purpose they have indentified six key online customers which were reliable/prompt responses, access, ease of use, attentiveness, security, and credibility. They have prepared questionnaire as data collection tool and done the survey of 270 full time and part time students and undergraduate students of U.S.A. the finding of this research confirmed that there is a strong and positive relationship between online retailers' service quality and their customer satisfaction. They found that three dimensions, reliable/prompt responses (service),

attentiveness, and ease of use, had significant impacts on both customers' perceived overall service quality and their satisfaction.

Persson, c. (2001) studied "strategies for enhancing customer interaction in electronic retailing". The objectives of his study were to examine the potential for e-commerce by identifying and analysing factors that are important for the consumers in making use of the new medium. The results of the studies indicate that all three strategies can give important contributions to the establishment of ease-of-use in e-commerce. The multi-channel retailing strategy seems to be the most useful strategy in the short run. The analytical technology strategy and the hypermedia interface strategy have the potential to become important strategies in the future of e-commerce.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

It is a systematic way to solve a problem. It is a science of studying how research is to be carried out. Essentially, the procedures by which researchers go about their work describing, explaining and predicting phenomena are called research methodology. It is also defined as the study of methods by which knowledge is gained. Its aim is to give the work plan of research.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To find the consumer behaviour in online shopping.
- To find the online shopping problems in flipkart.
- To identify the level of satisfaction derive by the consumer

SAMPLE SIZE

For the study, sample sizes of 50 respondents were selected.

TOOLS USED

Analyzing the data drawing its conclusion form. Most research studied result in large volume of raw data that must be suitably reduced so that same can be read easily and can be used for further analysis.

The tools used are:

- Simple percentage method
- Ranking method

SIMPLE PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS

1. Percentage Analysis for Gender of the Respondents:
Table showing the Gender of the respondents:

TABLE: 1

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	30	60
Female	20	40
Total	50	100

Interpretation

From the table it can be inferred that, 60% of the respondents are male, 40% of the respondents are female.

2. Percentage Analysis for age group of Respondents:

TABLE:2 Table showing the age group of the Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage
Below 15	3	6
15-30	20	40
31-45	16	32
Above 45	11	22
Total	50	100

Interpretation

From the table it can be inferred that,6% of the respondents are in the age group of below 15 years, 40% of the respondents are in the age group of 15 years to 30 years,32% of the respondents are in the age group of 31 years to 45 years,22% of the respondents are in the age group of above 45 years.

3. Percentage Analysis for Number of Family Members of Respondents:

TABLE: 3 Table showing the Number of Family Members of respondents

Family members	Frequency	Percentage
Up to 3 members	14	28
3-5 members	23	46
Above 5 member	13	26
Total	50	100

Interpretation

From the table it can be inferred that, 28% of the respondents have 3 members in the family, 46% of the respondents have 3-5 members in the family, 26% of the respondents have more than 5 members in the family.

4. Percentage Analysis for monthly Income of the respondents:

TABLE: 4 Table showing the monthly income of respondents

Monthly income	Frequency	Percentage
Below 10000	10	20
10000-20000	30	60
21000-30000	7	14
Above 30000	3	6
Total	50	100

Interpretation

From the table it can be inferred that, 20% of the respondents earn below rs.10000, 60% of the respondents earn Rs.10000-20000, 14% of the respondents earn Rs.21000-30000, 6% of the respondents earn more than 30000.

RANKING ANALYSIS

5. Percentage Analysis for occupation of the respondents:

TABLE:5 Table showing the occupation of the respondents

Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
Student	15	30
Employee	29	58
Homemaker	6	12
Others	0	0
Total	50	100

Interpretation

From the table it can referred that, 30% of therespondentsarestudents,58% of the respondents are employee, 12% of the respondents are home maker, 0% of the respondents are the others.

6. Percentage Analysis for frequency of buying products through flipkart of the respondents :

TABLE: 6 Table showing the buying products through flipkart of the respondents

Buying product	Frequency	Percentage
Weekly	14	28
Monthly	25	50
Yearly	11	22
Total	50	100

Interpretation

From the table it can referred that, 28% of the respondents buy weekly through flipkart, 50% of the respondents buy monthly through flipkart, 22% of the respondents buy yearly through flipkart.

7. Percentage Analysis for awareness about flipkart of the respondents

TABLE: 7Table showing the awareness of the respondents

Awareness Through	Frequency	Percentage
Friends	7	14
Advertisement	18	36
Relatives	21	42
Others	4	8
Total	50	100

Interpretation

From the table it can referred that, 14% of the respondents come to know about flipkart through friends, 36% of the respondents are aware of flipkart through advertisement, 42% of the respondents are aware of flipkart through relatives, 8% of the respondents are aware of flipkart through others.

8. Percentage Analysis for product purchase flipkart online shopping of the respondents :

TABLE: 8 Table showing the product purchase through in online shopping of respondents

Product of purchase	Frequency	Percentage
Mobile phone	22	44
Pen drive	11	22
Watches	11	22
Memory card	6	12
Total	50	100

Interpretation

From the table it can referred that, 44% of the respondents buy mobile phone, 22% of the respondents buy pen drive, 22% of the respondents buy watches, 12% of the respondents buy memory card.

FINDINGS

- Maximum 60%of respondents are male.
- Maximum 40% of respondents are between 15-30.
- Maximum 46% of respondents are between 3-5 members in a family.
- Maximum 58% of the respondents are employee.
- Maximum 60% of the respondent’s monthly income is more than 20000.

- Maximum 50% of the respondent of monthly buying product in filpkart.
- Maximum 42% of the respondents of awareness through in online relatives.
- Maximum 44% of the respondents of product purchase through online in mobiles phone.

SUGGESTIONS

- Only educated people are more aware of online shopping so focus should be made on people who are not aware of online purchase.
- To provide better security against malpractices.
- To improve the advertisement of online shopping.
- To reduce delivery charges and implement more offers to attract new customers.
- To make quick delivery of products.
- To make quick exchange of exchange of products in case of defect and size variation.
- To take corrective actions if any complaints are encountered by the customer.

CONCLUSION

On the basis of the present study concludes that the online customers are satisfied. This research explicitly indicates that filpkart online marketer should give were importance on price factor and after sale factor. In this competitive world, online marketer should have to offer new scheme day to day to attract the new customers.

Online shopping is becoming more popular day to day with the increase in the stage of world wide web known as www.understanding customer’s need for online selling has become challenge for marketers. In conclusion, having access to online shopping has truly revolutionized and influenced our society as a whole. This use of technology has opened new doors and opportunities that enable for aa more convenient lifestyle today. Variety, quick service and reduced prices were three significant ways a which online shopping led to the possibilities of fraud and privacy conflicts. Through privacy and security policies, website designers doing. By doing so, society a will continue to depend upon online shopping, which will allow it to remain a tremendous success in future.

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